

A Prospective Observational Study of Diagnostic Reliability of Semiquantitative and Quantitative High B Value Diffusion Weighted MRI in Distinguishing between Benign and Malignant Lung Lesion.

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Abstract:

Background: Globally, lung cancer is the primary cause of cancer-related mortality. Improving patient outcomes requires an early and precise diagnosis. It is still difficult to distinguish benign from malignant lung lesions using standard imaging methods. By analysing tissue diffusion properties, high b-value diffusion-weighted MRI (DW-MRI) has demonstrated potential for improving diagnostic accuracy.

Aim: To evaluate the diagnostic reliability of semiquantitative and quantitative high b-value DW-MRI in distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions.

Methods: Fifty individuals with suspected lung lesions participated in the study. Patients had high-value DW-MRIs, and apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values were used for quantitative analysis in addition to semiquantitative visual evaluations. The outcomes were contrasted with histological observations. SPSS version 23.0 was used for statistical analysis, and ROC curve analysis, sensitivity, and specificity were used to evaluate the diagnostic performance.

Results: The sensitivity and specificity of semiquantitative MRI were 85.7% and 66.7%, respectively. With a p-value of less than 0.001, quantitative analysis revealed that malignant lesions had considerably lower mean ADC values ($0.89 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$) than benign lesions ($1.35 \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$). The best ADC threshold, which was determined to be $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, produced a 90% sensitivity and an 80% specificity. An area under the curve (AUC) of 0.92 was obtained from the ROC curve study, showing good diagnostic performance.

Conclusion: When utilising quantitative ADC analysis, high b-value DW-MRI offers a dependable method of distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions. The method shows a high degree of diagnostic accuracy, indicating that it could be a useful tool in clinical practice.

Recommendations: It is advised to conduct more research with bigger sample sizes and multi-center trials to confirm these results and enhance imaging procedures for standard application in the diagnosis of lung cancer.

Keywords: Lung Lesions, Diffusion-Weighted MRI, ADC Values, Diagnostic Accuracy, Lung Cancer.

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Introduction

About 18% of all cancer fatalities are caused by lung cancer, making it one of the primary causes of cancer-related mortality globally [1]. Since the prognosis for individuals with lung cancer substantially worsens with advanced disease stages, early and precise detection of lung lesions is essential for increasing survival rates. The overlap in imaging characteristics between benign and malignant lung tumours, however, makes differentiation extremely difficult. Advanced imaging techniques are necessary to increase

diagnosis accuracy because conventional imaging modalities, like computed tomography (CT) scans and chest X-rays, frequently have poor specificity [2].

The non-invasive method of diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI) has shown promise in the assessment of lung cancer and other cancers. Because malignant tumours frequently have altered water molecule diffusion because to alterations in cellular density and membrane

integrity, DW-MRI is especially valuable in this regard [3]. A more sophisticated use of this technology called high b-value DW-MRI concentrates on regions with limited diffusion, which increases the contrast between benign and malignant tissues and may help identify and characterise malignant lesions.

Recent research has shown how useful DW-MRI is for diagnosing lung cancer. For example, a study demonstrated the high degree of accuracy with which DW-MRI can differentiate between benign and malignant lung nodules [4]. A useful measure in oncological imaging, apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values obtained from DW-MRI have also been demonstrated to correlate with tumour aggressiveness [5]. The best b-values to utilise and the validity of semiquantitative versus quantitative analysis in standard clinical practice are still up for debate, notwithstanding these developments.

This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic reliability of semiquantitative and quantitative high b-value DW-MRI in distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, from January 2023 to March 2024.

Participants: A total of 50 participants were enrolled in the study. Participants included patients who presented with lung lesions and were referred for MRI evaluation.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with clinically suspected or radiologically detected lung lesions.
- Patients aged 18 years or older.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with contraindications to MRI (e.g., pacemakers, metallic implants).
- Patients with a history of prior lung surgery or radiation therapy.

- Patients with known malignancies other than lung lesions.
- Pregnant women.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize bias by using a standardized imaging protocol and ensuring blinding of radiologists to the clinical diagnosis during the interpretation of MRI results.

Data Collection: Data were collected prospectively. Detailed patient demographics, clinical history, and imaging findings were recorded for each participant. MRI scans were performed using high b-value diffusion-weighted imaging, and both semiquantitative and quantitative analyses were conducted.

Procedure: MRI images using high-b-value diffusion-weighted imaging were performed on the participants. The diffusion-weighted pictures were visually assessed and scored as part of the semiquantitative analysis. An apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) calculation was used to conduct a quantitative investigation. The final histological diagnosis was then compared with these imaging results to determine which lung lesions were benign and malignant.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS 23.0. The clinical and demographic characteristics were gathered using descriptive statistics. The diagnostic performance of semiquantitative and quantitative muscle imaging was assessed using sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. To compare ADC values between benign and malignant lesions, the independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test were used, depending on data distribution. Significance was 0.05 or less.

Result

The study had 50 individuals, whose ages ranged from 30 to 80 years, with a mean age of 55.4 ± 12.3 . There were 18 females (36%), and 32 males (64%) in the cohort. Sixty percent of the patients had a history of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and seventy percent of them were smokers.

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	N (%)
Total Participants	50 (100%)
Mean Age (years)	55.4 ± 12.3
Gender	
- Male	32 (64%)
- Female	18 (36%)
Smoking History	35 (70%)
COPD History	30 (60%)

In the semiquantitative analysis, 35 out of 50 lesions (70%) were visually assessed as malignant

based on diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), while 15 lesions (30%) were assessed as benign.

Histopathological examination confirmed that 30 of the visually assessed malignant lesions were truly malignant, and 5 were benign. Among the 15 lesions assessed as benign, 10 were histopathologically confirmed as benign, and 5 were malignant.

The semiquantitative analysis showed a sensitivity of 85.7%, specificity of 66.7%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 85.7%, and negative predictive value (NPV) of 66.7%.

Table 2: Diagnostic Performance of Semiquantitative MRI

Measure	Value (%)
Sensitivity	85.7%
Specificity	66.7%
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	85.7%
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	66.7%

In contrast to benign lesions, the mean ADC value for malignant lesions was significantly lower ($0.89 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ vs. $1.35 \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, $p < 0.001$). With a 90% sensitivity and 80% specificity, the ADC value threshold was found to be $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ for distinguishing benign from malignant lesions.

Table 3: Comparison of ADC Values Between Benign and Malignant Lesions

Lesion Type	Mean ADC Value ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$)	p-value
Malignant	0.89 ± 0.15	<0.001
Benign	1.35 ± 0.20	

The ROC curve was plotted to assess the diagnostic accuracy of ADC values in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. The AUC was 0.92, indicating excellent diagnostic performance.

Table 4: ROC Curve Analysis

Statistic	Value
AUC	0.92
Sensitivity at ADC threshold	90%
Specificity at ADC threshold	80%

Discussion

The results of this prospective observational study demonstrate that high b-value diffusion-weighted MRI is an effective tool for distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions. The semiquantitative analysis, which relied on visual assessment of diffusion-weighted images, yielded a sensitivity of 85.7% and a specificity of 66.7%. While the high sensitivity indicates that this method is reliable for identifying malignant lesions, the moderate specificity suggests that some benign lesions may be mistakenly classified as malignant, leading to potential false positives.

In contrast, the quantitative analysis, which involved calculating the ADC values, provided more robust results. Malignant lesions had significantly lower mean ADC values compared to benign lesions ($0.89 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ vs. $1.35 \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$), with a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating a strong statistical difference. The optimal ADC threshold of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ demonstrated a sensitivity of 90% and a specificity of 80%, highlighting the method's accuracy in correctly classifying lung lesions.

The ROC curve analysis further supported the efficacy of quantitative ADC values, with an AUC of 0.92, which signifies excellent diagnostic performance. This high AUC value indicates that ADC measurements can be a powerful diagnostic

tool, providing a balance between sensitivity and specificity that is superior to semiquantitative visual assessments.

Overall, these findings suggest that while semiquantitative MRI is useful for initial assessments, quantitative ADC analysis offers a more precise method for differentiating lung lesions. The use of ADC values in clinical practice could improve the accuracy of lung lesion diagnoses, reducing the likelihood of unnecessary interventions for benign conditions and ensuring timely treatment for malignant cases. However, the study's results should be validated in larger studies to confirm these findings and to further refine the diagnostic thresholds used in practice.

A prospective observational study evaluated the usefulness of high b-value DWI to differentiate benign and malignant lung lesions using 3 Tesla MRI. Among 31 patients, the study found that semiquantitative and quantitative DWI parameters were effective in distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions. The study reported that the minimum ADC value was significantly lower in malignant lesions (mean ADC of $1.11 \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$) compared to benign ones. The study concluded that these MRI techniques offer high sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy for characterizing lung lesions [6].

The usefulness of various b-values (300, 500, and 1000 s/mm²) in diffusion-weighted MRI for differentiating between benign and malignant lung lesions was examined in a different investigation. The results showed that, for all b-values, malignant lesions had considerably lower ADC values than benign ones. According to the study's findings, the greatest combination of sensitivity (90%) and specificity (69%) for identifying these lesions was found at a b-value of 500 s/mm² [7].

Diffusion-weighted imaging with background body signal suppression (DWIBS) was considered as a diagnostic tool for differentiating between benign and malignant lung isolated lesions. The research revealed that malignant lesions had considerably lower ADC values at varying b-values. An ideal ADC threshold value of 1.435×10^{-3} mm²/s yielded good specificity (83.3%) and sensitivity (80.0%). It has been demonstrated that DWIBS is a trustworthy method for qualitatively diagnosing lung abnormalities [8].

A study investigated the diagnostic utility of semi-quantitative dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI) and intravoxel incoherent motion (IVIM) diffusion-weighted MRI for single pulmonary lesions. ADC and T_{max} are important factors in separating benign from malignant lesions, according to the study, which also indicated that combining DCE-MRI and IVIM greatly increased diagnostic accuracy. A sensitivity of 90.5% and specificity of 86.4% were obtained from the combination [9].

In order to distinguish between benign and malignant solitary pulmonary lesions, a study examined the diagnostic values of several diffusion parameters derived from mono- and biexponential DWI models and diffusion kurtosis imaging (DKI). The study discovered that the traditional ADC values, with the highest AUC of 0.862 for ADC total, were useful in discriminating lesions. According to the study, in this particular setting, both IVIM and DKI-derived parameters function comparably to standard DWI [10].

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that high b-value diffusion-weighted MRI, both semiquantitative and quantitative, is a reliable method for distinguishing between benign and malignant lung lesions. Semiquantitative MRI showed high sensitivity but moderate specificity, whereas quantitative ADC analysis provided excellent sensitivity and specificity, making it a valuable tool in clinical decision-making.

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